

Elastic plastic analysis of an encased composite beam with an inverted hybrid T-steel section

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ABSTRACT

The goal of this research is to carry out theoretical and experimental flexural elastic plastic analysis of the composite encased beams. The composite beam model here consists of an inverted formed hybrid T-beam section surrounded by concrete with minimum stirrups. The variable in this study are: thickness of steel plates that construct the inverted hybrid T-beam section, dimensions of concrete encasement and yield stress of steel plates of beam. Five groups of specimens had been tested till failure in order to investigate flexural behaviour, ultimate strength, cracking mechanism and deflection of beams.

Qualitative analysis of experimental results, experimental curves are shown, theoretical formulas are derived to verify the experimental results. It should be noted that this research is still going on.

Keywords: Composite, Steel-concrete, Hybrid, Inverted T-beam

1 INTRODUCTION

Using the encased composite beams has become flash reality up to date. This is due to numerous professional, technical, and structural aspects which those composite beams encompass. The two popular composite beams are the encased composite beam, which is the subject of this paper, and the traditional exposed composite beam. If satisfying the requirements of concrete cover (encasement), the encased composite beam provides fully composite behaviour over the exposed traditional structure with shear connectors, and has a good property against earthquakes, good stiffness, energy absorption, and drastically reduces the possibility of local buckling of the steel beam. Good constructive performance and lower costs, leading to increasing application in the industry. It should be noted that encased steel beams completely and partially have higher resistance to fire and corrosion as be known. The horizontal shears between the steel beams and surrounded concrete can be considered to be transferred by natural bond and friction between the two. Shear connectors are not necessary when the natural bond is sufficient to achieve the desired steel-concrete interaction.

Many authors (1), (2) and (3) have worked on the partially encased composite beams with headed shear welded studs and I-beams. However, little experimental data is available for the case presented here of no shear connectors and no top flange of steel beam.

In other research, where reinforcing bars and headed shear studs were combined to provide the composite action, the longitudinal shear force transfer occurred mainly by friction forces acting at the interface among the concrete encasement and the structural steel beam [4].

2 STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS OF ENCASED MODEL

An elastic and plastic basic equations have been provided below to verify the experimental results.

Fig. 1. a) The beam experimental model; b) Composite model; c) Plastic analysis

Theoretical elastic moment:

Modulus ratio (5):
$$n = \frac{200000}{4729.77\sqrt{f'_c}} \geq 6$$

$$\frac{B}{n} \frac{y_t^2}{2} = A_s [y_{st} + d' - y_t] \quad , \quad \frac{b}{2nA_s} y_t^2 + y_t - (y_{st} + d') = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$I_{tr} = \frac{b}{n} \frac{y_t^3}{3} + I_s + A_s [y_{st} + d' - y_t]^2$$

$$M_c = 0.45 f'_c \frac{n I_{tr}}{y_t} \quad , \quad M_s = 0.66 F_y \frac{I_{tr}}{y_b - d} \quad (2)$$

Where:

A_s Area of inverted steel t-beam.

f'_c Compressive strength of concrete.

F_y Yield stress of steel.

Theoretical ultimate moment capacity:

$$y = y_t, \quad y = \frac{600}{600 + f_y} (H - d), \quad a = \beta_1 y, \quad y = a / \beta_1 \quad (3)$$

For $f'_c \leq 27.58$ MPa, $\beta_1 = 0.85$

For $f'_c > 27.58$ MPa, $\beta_1 = 0.85 - (5/689.5) (f'_c - 27.58) \leq 0.65$

$$C_c = 0.85 f'_c B a$$

$$C_w = (f_{yw} - 0.85 f'_c) (y - d') t_w$$

$$T_w = f_{yw} [d_w + d' - y] t_w, \quad T_f = f_{yf} A_f$$

$$C_c + C_w = T_w + T_f, \quad y = \frac{f_{yw} A_w + f_{yf} A_f - 0.85 f'_c d' t_w + 2 f_{yw} d' t_w}{0.85 f'_c B \beta_1 + 2 f_{yw} t_w - 0.85 f'_c t_w} \leq \beta_1 y \quad (4)$$

$$M_p = 0.90 \left\{ C_c [y - 0.5 a] + C_w \left[\frac{y - d'}{2} \right] + T_w \left[\frac{d_w - (y - d')}{2} \right] + T_f [H - y - d - 0.5 t_f] \right\} \quad (5)$$

2 PROPERTIS OF MODELS

Table 1. shows the material properties that have been involved in the five group models. Fig. 2a, b and c show steel inverted hybrid steel T beam during the fabrication and forming the stirrups. Fig. 2d shows the composite beam model under the test.

Table 1. Properties of materials

Group name	Sample	Gross section		Thick. of web t_w (mm)	Thick. of flange t_f (mm)	Yield stress of web f_{yw} (MPa)	Yield stress of flange f_{yf} (MPa)	Concrete strength f'_c (MPa)
		B (cm)	H (cm)					
G1	B1	25	25	8	8	356.4	493.1	32
	B2				10	352.3	489.9	
	B3				16	361.3	498.5	
G2	B1	25	25	10	8	356.4	493.1	
	B2				10	352.3	489.9	
	B3				16	361.3	498.5	
G3	B1	25	25	16	8	356.4	493.1	
	B2				10	352.3	489.9	
	B3				16	361.3	498.5	
G4	B1	25	25	8	8	356.4	493.1	
	B2	35						
G5	B1	25	25	16	16	361.3	498.5	
	B2	35						

a)

b)

c)

d)

Fig. 2. a, b, c) Fabrication of steel beam; d) Composite beam model under the testing machine

3 EXPERIMENTAL PROCESS

The experiments were carried out gradually with a load interval of 0.5Ton, 1Ton ... etc. until the models collapsed, in the meantime deflection readings were taken. The composite action between the surrounded concrete and the steel beam failed due to excessive cracks. Fig. 3 shows experimental curves for the models that have different thickness of plates.

Group G1: 1 ton = 10 KN

Group G2: 1 ton = 10 KN

Fig. 3. Experimental curves

Table 2 shows qualitative analysis of experiment results. Figure 4 shows failure progression of model B2 of Group 4. Figure 5 shows failure progression of model B2 of Group 5.

Table 2. Qualitative analysis of experiment results

Group	Specimens	Qualitative analysis of experiment results
G1	All	Cracks at the centre of beam under loads Vertical and inclined
G2	All	Cracks at the centre of beam under loads Vertical and inclined
G3	All	Cracks at the centre of beam under loads Vertical and inclined
G4	All	Cracks at the centre of beam under loads Cracks were heavy
G5	All	Cracks at the centre of beam under loads Cracks were heavy

The change in the width of the studied models, B, affects the collapse mechanism of the composite beam. Longitudinal cracks formed and increased in width, then began to take a transverse shape and continued until the concrete collapsed in the tension zone of the beam.

Fig. 4. Failure mechanisms of beam B2 of Group G4

Fig. 5. Failure mechanisms of beam B2 of Group G5

Tables 3 and 4 outline the outcome of study.

Table 3. Elastic analysis summary

Group	Model	Elastic analysis			
		Experiment		Theory	
		Def. mm	M _e KN.m.	Def. mm	M _e KN.m.
G1	B1	11.4	62.5	11.3	64.0
	B2	11.3	65.6	10.8	67.1
	B3	9.8	68.8	9.7	73.3
G2	B1	11.3	64.0	11.2	65.1
	B2	11.0	65.6	10.7	68.2
	B3	9.9	71.9	9.7	74.4

G3	B1	11.0	65.6	10.9	68.5
	B2	10.6	68.8	10.5	71.5
	B3	10.0	75.0	9.7	77.6
G4	B1	11.4	62.5	11.3	64.0
	B2	11.3	87.5	10.9	92.1
G5	B1	10.0	75.0	9.7	77.6
	B2	10.0	106.3	9.3	109.7

Table 4. Plastic analysis summary

Plastic analysis				
Group	Model	Ultimate moment		$\frac{M_{\text{experiment}}}{M_{\text{theory}}}$
		Exper.	Theory	
		Mu (KN.m)	Mu (KN.m)	%
G1	B1	87.5	88.9	0.98
	B2	96.3	97.7	0.99
	B3	118.8	121.1	0.98
G2	B1	90.6	92.5	0.98
	B2	100	101.3	0.99
	B3	121.9	124.5	0.98
G3	B1	103.1	103.5	1.0
	B2	112.5	112.1	1.0
	B3	131.3	130.4	1.01
G4	B1	87.5	88.9	0.98
	B2	118.8	120.2	0.99
G5	B1	131.3	130.4	1.01
	B2	175.0	179.1	0.98

4 CONCLUSION

The structural behaviour of encased beams was investigated by full-scale flexural tests. According to the test program outlined in this paper, several conclusions can be drawn and are summarized as follows.

Specimens were considered to have failed when the concrete cracked, starting near the mid-length of the beam and progressively spreading towards the supports

Increasing the thickness from 8 mm to 16 mm of the lower flange of hybrid steel beam increases the cross-sectional bending resistance from 25% to 35%. As the web thickness increases, this ratio increases up to maximum of 13%.

Increasing the gross-sectional width of concrete encasement does not significantly affect the elastic-ductile behavior.

From the load-deflection curves, it is shown that the linear behavior of each model takes more than half of the total behavior range until collapse.

Splitting of encasement came after extensive cracking.

The elastic and ultimate capacities of the specimens tested were close for all cases to those from the analytical equations.

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